

DIRECT NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS OF HORIZONTAL-AXIS WIND TURBINE BLADE SECTION BY CONSIDERING AEROELASTIC VIBRATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Innovative wind power technologies have led to wind turbines with significantly longer and more flexible blade designs to meet the rise in green energy demands. To capture all details of vorticities, flow separation, and pressure distribution on the surface of the blades by considering their flap-wise oscillations a highly accurate numerical analysis over a mid-section of a wind turbine is performed. A spectral-hp element method which is employed to capture all details of flow structure on the surface of NACA0012 wind turbine aerofoil for different angles of attack. The simulations were performed at $Re=1.30 \times 10^5$ and the blades have harmonic oscillations at the Mach number of $Ma_\infty=0.4$. The results show that the flow separation point is significantly affected due to the vibrations. Flow separation occurs at $X/C=0.580$ over the stationary blade, while it happens much faster at $X/C=0.172$ on the surface of the oscillating airfoil. Flow detachment and reattachment due to the flap-wise oscillations could be the main reason for faster separation and additional flow disturbance.

Keywords: Wind turbines; Direct numerical simulations; blades vibrations; flow separation; NACA airfoil.

1. INTRODUCTION

Wind energy as a renewable and clean source of energy has been widely used to generate electrical power by using different types of wind turbines in complex wind farm layouts. Wind turbines currently generate only 5% of the electricity requirement [1], but this is expected to increase significantly over the next few years due to global warming and to reduce carbon emissions to the environment. Nowadays, wind turbines are becoming larger and bigger to produce more electrical power. In offshore wind farms in the UK, the wind turbines also became larger. Using larger wind turbine blades indicate that the aeroelastic oscillations of the blades cannot be neglected and must be included in the numerical models to provide a more realistic analysis of the efficiency of horizontal-axis wind turbines (HAWTs). Previous numerical studies over wind turbine blades with different airfoils, such as NACA0012, were mostly focused on low-fidelity models, such as the numerical study of

Ekaterinaris [2] and Barakos & Drikakis [3] over two-dimensional oscillating airfoils. Moreover, many simplifying assumptions were made in those studies to investigate the aerodynamic characteristics of wind turbine blades. However, due to the vibrations of the blades, low-fidelity methods such as the Reynolds average Navier-Stokes (RANS) model cannot predict instantaneous variations of the vorticities and complex flow behavior over wind turbine blades. In addition, such important aerodynamic characteristics have not been investigated yet.

Alam and Sandham [4] performed a numerical simulation on laminar separation bubble (LSB) formation and onset of transition over wind turbine aerofoil. It was observed that Kelvin-Helmholtz instability occurred in the separated shear-layer. Zhang et al. [5] modified the shape of a wind turbine airfoil to increase its efficiency. The results revealed that the transition occurs faster on the thinner airfoils. The main restriction of using high-fidelity methods is significant computation time in comparison with the RANS models. Wahidi et al. [6] experimentally investigated the flow structure and LSB formation over NACA4412 airfoil by using the PIV visualizations. It was observed that the flow separation point depends on the AoA of the airfoil. Naung et al. [7] performed a numerical investigation to analyze the flow instabilities in a separated region over a wind turbine blade. They concluded that the inflow wake has an impact on the flow separation and vortex generation over the blades. Gaster [8] investigated the formation of LSB over airfoils at different Reynolds numbers. It was concluded that the size of the bubbles depends on the pressure gradient and separation point over the surface of the airfoil

To overcome the limitations of the low-fidelity numerical models and to capture instantaneous flow separation and vortex generation in different aerodynamic problems, high-fidelity methods like the spectral-hp element method are developed to investigate complex flow behavior over the wind turbine blades [9]. This code provides the capability to consider the aeroelastic vibrations with a mapping function and moving reference frame (MRF). This method provides the ability to model complex flows by considering all important and real physical conditions.

This method is based on an open-source solver (NEKTAR++), which is developed at Imperial College London [10]. A recent study of Nakhchi et al. [11] showed that flap-wise oscillations of the wind turbine blades have a significant impact on their aerodynamic characteristics. However, previous studies were mostly focused on pitch-wise oscillations of the airfoils using experiments or low-fidelity numerical models. The aim of this study is to propose a high-fidelity direct numerical simulation (DNS) to investigate the effects of flap-wise oscillations of the wind turbine blades on the flow separation, vortex shedding, and other important physical parameters on the surface of the oscillating wind turbine blades.

2. PHYSICAL DESCRIPTION

The schematic view of the horizontal-axis wind turbine with the details of flap-wise oscillations is shown in Fig. 1. The mid-section of the wind turbine blade is NACA0012 which is popular in the design of wind turbine blades. The wind turbine rotates with a constant angular velocity of Ω , and the flow is assumed to be uniform.

FIGURE 1: SCHEMATIC VIEW OF AEROELASTIC OSCILLATIONS OF HAWT BLADES.

3. MATHEMATICAL FORMULATION

In this study, the spectral-hp element method, which is a popular high-order method in complex aerodynamic analysis, has been used for DNS simulations. The flow is assumed to be fully turbulent, transient, and incompressible. The governing equations momentum and continuity equations in tensor form can be expressed as:

$$\partial_t \mathbf{u} + (\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{u} = -\nabla p + \nu \nabla^2 \mathbf{u} \quad (1)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0 \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{u} , p and ν are the velocity, pressure, and kinematic viscosity. The moving reference frame (MRF) function of the NEKTAR++ solver is used for the CFD analysis on the UK national supercomputer (ARCHER2) cluster using 16 nodes with 2048 CPU cores at 2.2 GHz. The latest master version of the code is utilized for the DNS simulations. The definitions of aerodynamic forces on the NACA0012 airfoil used in this study are provided in Figure 2. The airfoil has a chord length (C) of 0.25 m with a span length of $L_s=0.2$. The angle of attack (AoA) is selected in the range of ($0^\circ < \alpha < 20^\circ$) in the present DNS

study. The inlet velocity is uniform, and the Reynolds number ($Re = U_{in} C / \nu$) is kept constant at $Re=1.30 \times 10^5$. The air density is 1.2 kg/m^3 , and viscosity (μ) is selected as $1.788 \times 10^{-5} \text{ kg/(m.s)}$.

FIGURE 2: AERODYNAMIC FORCES AND DESIGN PARAMETERS ON NACA0012 AIRFOIL.

The spectral-hp element method decomposes the computational field into smaller domains as $\Omega = \cup_{e \in \mathcal{E}} \Omega_e$, where Ω is the computation domain and Ω_e is a sub-domain of the mesh. The mapping function converts the local cartesian coordinates into a reference coordinate system of (ξ_1, ξ_2) with the mapped space as $x_1 = \chi_1^e(\xi_1, \xi_2)$, $x_2 = \chi_2^e(\xi_1, \xi_2)$.

The Galerkin scheme is chosen for the unsteady incompressible flow modelling on the horizontal-axis WT airfoil at the Reynolds number of 1.30×10^5 .

Equation (1) can be expressed as $\partial_t \mathbf{u} = N(\mathbf{u}) - \nabla p + \nu \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{u})$. In which $N(\mathbf{u}) = \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla)$ and $\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{u}) = \nabla^2 \mathbf{u}$ are the convective and diffusive terms of the N-S equations, respectively. The Poisson and Helmholtz terms, can be expressed as:

$$\nabla^2 p^{n+1} = \frac{1}{\Delta t} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}^* \quad (3)$$

$$\nabla^2 \mathbf{u}^{n+1} - \frac{\alpha_0}{\nu \Delta t} \mathbf{u}^{n+1} = -\frac{\mathbf{u}^*}{\nu \Delta t} + \frac{1}{\nu} \nabla p^{n+1} \quad (4)$$

By integration of the N-S equations and using discretized advection, Poisson and Helmholtz terms, the momentum equation in $n+1$ th time-step is discretized as [12]:

$$\frac{\gamma_0 \mathbf{u}^{n+1} - \sum_{q=0}^{J_i-1} \alpha_q \mathbf{u}^{n-q}}{\Delta t} = \sum_{q=0}^{J_e-1} \beta_q N(\mathbf{u}^{n-q}) - \nabla p^{n+1} + \nu \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{u}^{n+1}) \quad (5)$$

In which J_e and J_i are the explicit and implicit terms. Equation (5) can be written as:

$$\frac{\gamma_0 \mathbf{u}^{n+1} - \mathbf{u}^+}{\Delta t} = N^+ - \nabla p^{n+1} + \nu \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{u}^{n+1}) \quad (6)$$

where $\mathbf{u}^+ = \sum_{q=0}^{J_i-1} \alpha_q \mathbf{u}^{n-q}$ and $N^+ = \sum_{q=0}^{J_e-1} \beta_q N(\mathbf{u}^{n-q})$.

For the outlet of the domain, high-order boundary conditions are imposed to capture the details of vorticities in the wake region and for better convergence of the simulations. The upper and lower walls of the domain are set as periodic and

uniform inflow boundary condition is imposed at the inlet of the domain. The high-order pressure-outlet boundary condition can be expressed as [12]:

$$p^{n+1} = \nu \mathbf{n} \cdot \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}^{*,n+1} \cdot \mathbf{n} - \frac{1}{2} |\mathbf{u}^{*,n+1}|^2 S_0(\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{u}^{*,n+1}) + f_b^{n+1} \cdot \mathbf{n} \quad (7)$$

Where $S_0(\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{u}) = \frac{1}{2} (1 - \tanh \frac{\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{u}}{u_0 \delta})$ is a step function, u_0 is the characteristic velocity, and δ is a positive constant value [13]. The pressure outlet BC can be written as:

$$\nabla \mathbf{u}^{n+1} \cdot \mathbf{n} = \frac{1}{\nu} [p^{n+1} \mathbf{n} + \frac{1}{2} |\mathbf{u}^{*,n+1}|^2 S_0(\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{u}^{*,n+1}) - \nu (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}^{*,n+1}) \mathbf{n} - f_b^{n+1}] \quad (8)$$

More details about the discretization and numerical modelling in the spectral-hp element method can be found in Ref. [11]. The solution flowchart based on the spectral-hp element method and the methodology of solving the advection, Poisson, and Helmholtz terms, are provided in Figure 3.

FIGURE 3: SIMULATION METHOD OF THE SPECTRAL-HP ELEMENT METHOD IN NEKTAR++ OPEN-SOURCE CODE.

The details mesh used in this study is provided in Figure 4. The airfoil has harmonic oscillations with a frequency of $f=5.2\text{Hz}$ and amplitude of $A=0.01C$, where C is the chord length of the blade. A refined mesh is used in the wake region to capture the vorticities and laminar separation bubble precisely in this region. Inflated boundary layer mesh with eight layers and a growth rate of 1.1 is used in the present study to make sure the wall+ values remain in acceptable range. The mesh is presented by using polynomial order of $P=5$. It indicates that the edges of each element are divided into 5 elements.

FIGURE 4: MESH GENERATION OVER THE OSCILLATING WIND TURBINE AIRFOIL WITH $P=5$.

A grid independence study is performed in Table 1 to find the most appropriate polynomial order to capture the flow separation point on the surface of the wind turbine airfoil precisely. The grid test study is performed at $Re=1.30 \times 10^5$ at $AoA=20^\circ$ over the non-oscillating wind turbine blade. It can be seen that $P=8$ can accurately capture the flow separation point on the surface of the blade with a deviation less than 0.2% compared to $P=9$. Therefore, $P=8$ is selected for further simulations. A grid study in span direction is also performed to find the required number of FFT planes in span direction. It was observed that $N_p=64$ is suitable enough to capture all details of vorticities and flow separation on the surface of both vibrating and non-oscillating wind turbine blade with a dimensionless span length of $L_z=0.2$.

Figure 5 shows that all wall+ values (Δx^+ , Δy^+ , Δz^+) are in an acceptable range. $\Delta y^+ < 1$ over the whole blade indicate the laminar viscous sub-layer is fully resolved in the turbulent boundary layer on the surface of the airfoil, and all details of the flow separation are captured accurately.

Table 1 Grid sensitivity analysis of flow separation point over wind turbine airfoil at $AoA=0^\circ$.

P-order	X_{sep}/C	Deviation
4	0.717	8.64%
6	0.655	6.56%
7	0.612	5.06%
8	0.581	0.17%
9	0.580	-

FIGURE 5: WALL+ VALUES IN ALL DIRECTIONS OVER THE WIND TURBINE AIRFOIL.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Before doing the DNS computations, it is essential to validate the numerical results with experimental data over the NACA0012 airfoil at a constant Reynolds number. It can be seen in Fig. 5 that the results are in good agreement with the experimental results of Lee and Gerontakos [14], and the numerical simulation results of Shen et al. [15]. It is seen that the lift coefficient, C_L of this DNS study, is in good agreement with the experiments at $Re = 130000$ for different angles of attacks. The comparison with experimental data shows that stall capturing in this study over the non-oscillating airfoil is more accurate compared to the numerical results of Shen. It can be observed that the stall is occurred at $AoA=13^\circ$ for this case.

FIGURE 6: VALIDATION OF LIFT COEFFICIENT OVER NON-OSCILLATING WIND TURBINE AIRFOIL AT $Re=1.30 \times 10^5$.

The pressure coefficient (C_p) on the surface of a NACA-0012 aerofoil is validated with the experimental data of Rinoie and Takemura [16] in Figure 7. The validation is performed at specific Reynolds number of $Re=1.30 \times 10^5$. The validation

shows that the high-order numerical model used in this study can accurately predict the pressure coefficient on the surface of the wind turbine blade at different dimensionless axial positions (X/C). The validation is performed at $AoA=0^\circ$. It can be seen that the pressure coefficient is high close to leading edge, and then it starts to gradually decrease by moving to the trailing edge.

FIGURE 7: VALIDATION OF LIFT COEFFICIENT OVER NON-OSCILLATING WIND TURBINE AIRFOIL AT $Re=1.30 \times 10^5$.

Figure 8 shows the effects of vibrations on instant vortex generation on the surface of the wind turbine airfoil. The results revealed that the harmonic vibrations have a significant impact on the flow separation point. The flow separation occurred at $X/C=0.580$ over the stationary blade, while it happens at $X/C=0.172$ over the vibrating blade. Moreover, additional flow disturbance is captured on both pressure sides and suction sides of the wind turbine airfoil. Physically speaking, the additional energy imposed on the turbulent airflow on the blade surface at $Re = 1.3 \times 10^5$ is the main source of additional unsteadiness and vortex generation on the surface of the blade. Flow detachment and reattachment due to the flap-wise oscillations is the main reason for faster separation and additional flow disturbance.

FIGURE 8: THE EFFECTS OF VIBRATIONS ON VORTICITY GENERATION ON THE SURFACE OF THE WIND TURBINE BLADE.

Figure 9 illustrates the effects of the wind turbine blade vibrations on the wake profile at the downstream region of the trailing edge. The time-averaged wake profile is plotted at $X/C=1.25$ in the wake region. The results show that the wake profile is significantly affected due to the vibrations. More fluctuations in the wake profile (U^*), which is defined as U/U_{ref} is detected at the centre of the wake region. The size of the separated area is much larger for the higher angle of attack of 14 compared to the $AoA=8^\circ$ case.

FIGURE 9: THE EFFECTS OF VIBRATIONS ON WAKE PROFILE IN THE SEPARATED REGION ON THE SURFACE OF THE BLADE.

According to the study of Rahmati et al. [17], the airflow parameters due to the harmonic vibrations with a vibration frequency of ($\omega = 2\pi f$), can be written as:

$$Q = \bar{Q} + A_Q \sin(\omega t) + B_Q \cos(\omega t) \quad (9)$$

Where \bar{Q} , A_Q and B_Q are the coefficients of the parameters.

With rearranging Eq. (9) in $\frac{\partial Q}{\partial t} = R(Q)$, we have:

$$\omega(A_Q \cos(\omega t) - B_Q \sin(\omega t)) = R'(Q) \quad (10)$$

By using these three algebraic equations, the unknown parameters \bar{Q} , A_Q and B_Q can be evaluated. During a harmonic

vibration period, the pressure can be expressed as $P = P_{Avg} + P_A \sin(\omega t) + P_B \cos(\omega t)$. The unsteady pressure coefficient (C_{p1}) and pressure phase angle (ϕ), can be computed by $C_{p1} = \sqrt{P_A^2 + P_B^2}$, and $\phi = \tan^{-1}(\frac{P_A}{P_B})$. The variations of the unsteady pressure coefficient and pressure phase angle over the surface of the oscillating wind turbine. Figure 10 shows the unsteady pressure coefficient (C_{p1}) changes on the wind turbine aerofoil at different angles of attack. At $AoA = 14^\circ$, the C_{p1} variations between the suction and pressure sides are larger near the leading edge due to the higher AoA s. After this point, the pressure values become twisted, and the fluctuations become greater due to the flow detachment and stronger vorticities in the separated shear layer. Because of the vibrations of the blade, the horizontal-axis wind turbine faces unsteady aerodynamic forces resulting from transient pressure distribution. In an aeroelastic analysis, unsteady pressure values are usually expressed in terms of the unsteady pressure coefficient and phase angle, which can be determined based on the transient variations in the pressure data.

Figure 11 demonstrates the variations of the pressure phase angle (ϕ) on the aerofoil surface for the $AoA=0^\circ$ and 14° . At $AoA = 0^\circ$, the pressure phase angle varies from -158° to 8° , while these variations are more noticeable at 14° and range from -142° to 78° on the pressure side. A similar trend is also captured on the suction side of the blade. The main physical reason for large phase angle variations is the larger flow separation area.

FIGURE 10: THE EFFECTS OF ANGLE OF ATTACK ON THE UNSTEADY PRESSURE COEFFICIENT OVER THE OSCILLATING WT BLADE.

FIGURE 11: THE EFFECTS OF ANGLE OF ATTACK ON THE UNSTEADY PHASE ANGLE OVER THE OSCILLATING WT BLADE.

Figure 12 shows the pressure contours at the mid-section of the oscillating and stationary wind turbine airfoil for different angles of attack ($AoA=0^\circ, 20^\circ$) at $Re=130,000$. The results show that the pressure is smaller on the suction side and higher on the pressure surface. The location of the peak pressure is mainly dependent on the angle of attack. The pressure difference between these faces creates the lift forces needed for the rotation of the wind turbine. It can be seen that in all cases, pressure bubbles are developed in the flow-separated region of the airfoil, and they shed away from the trailing edge. LSB formation is also clear on the suction side of the airfoil, especially on oscillating airfoils. By raising the AoA , the separated shear layer gets larger, and the evolution of pressure bubbles becomes sharper. Strong negative pressure contours are detected on the suction side of the NACA0012 airfoil at a higher angle of attack of 20° . It is observed that instantaneous pressure bubbles are also developed on the pressure surface of the oscillating blade due to the rolling up of the vorticity structures, which was seen on the surface of the oscillating wind turbine aerofoil.

(a) Stationary, $AoA=0^\circ$

(b) Oscillating, $AoA=0^\circ$

(c) Stationary, $AoA=20^\circ$

(d) Oscillating, $AoA=20^\circ$

FIGURE 12: THE EFFECTS OF VIBRATIONS ON CROSS-SECTION PRESSURE CONTOURS OVER WT AEROFOIL AT $Re=1.30 \times 10^5$ FOR TWO DIFFERENT ANGLES OF ATTACKS.

Power spectral density (PSD) of the pressure signals in the wake region of both stationary and oscillating wind turbine blade are captured at the specific point of $X/C=1.2$ close to the trailing edge. The PSD results are shown in Figure 12 with respect to the frequency. It can be seen that the oscillating blade generate more energy spectrum compared to the non-oscillating blade. The results show that the slope of the PSD lines for both stationary and oscillating airfoils fall below the $-5/3$ slope-line, which corresponds to the characteristic slope of the turbulent flow, and it illustrates the convergence of the measured signals.

FIGURE 13: PSD OF PRESSURE SIGNALS OVER THE STATIONERY AND OSCILLATING WIND TURBINE AIRFOIL.

5. CONCLUSION

In this study spectral-hp element method is used to investigate the flow characteristics over wind turbine airfoil by considering the flap-wise oscillations. The simulations were performed at $Re=1.30 \times 10^5$ for different angle of attacks. Different instantaneous and time-averaged aerodynamic characteristics on the surface of the oscillating airfoil are captured and compared with the non-oscillating blade. The main findings are as follows:

1. For all cases, pressure bubbles are developed in the flow separated region of the airfoil, and they shed away from the trailing edge. LSB formation is also clear on the suction side of the airfoil, especially on oscillating airfoils. By raising the AoA, the separated shear layer gets larger, the evolution of pressure bubbles becomes sharper.
2. Strong negative pressure contours are detected on the suction side of the wind turbine airfoil at higher angle of attack of 20° . It is observed that instantaneous pressure bubbles are also developed on the pressure surface of the oscillating blade due to the rolling up of the vorticity structures, which was seen on the surface of the oscillating wind turbine aerofoil.
3. The flow separation occurred at $X/C=0.580$ over the stationary blade, while it happens at $X/C=0.172$ over the vibrating blade. Physically speaking, the additional energy imposed to the turbulent airflow on the surface of the blade is the main source of unsteadiness and vortex generation on the surface of the blade.
4. Flow detachment and reattachment due to the flap-wise oscillations cause faster flow separation and additional flow disturbance.

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